

1 **On the use of a mesoscale masonry pattern representation in discrete** 2 **macro-element approach**

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7 **Abstract**

8 This paper presents numerical investigations using the mesoscale approach coupled with the discrete
9 macro-element approach for masonry structures, i.e., each macro-element represents a single unit stone.

10 At first, parametric analyses are performed on a U-shape masonry prototype made with stone. Nonlinear
11 static analyses are performed to investigate parameters that affect the results when a mesoscale masonry
12 pattern representation is adopted. Results demonstrate how mesoscale representation is a powerful
13 alternative to model unreinforced masonry structures within a discrete macro-element approach
14 (particularly if compared with classic homogeneous FE methodologies). However, one of the main
15 challenges in using the mesoscale approach for the structural assessment of masonry buildings, made
16 with stones having different dimensions, is the unit by unit description. The complexity of the problem,
17 and the amount of information needed, usually preclude the study of these structures deterministically.

18 To this end, a digital tool to generate randomised masonry patterns using a few input parameters is
19 proposed. A box structure is adopted as parent geometry, and ten masonry patterns with different
20 degrees of randomness are investigated by performing nonlinear static and dynamic simulations. The
21 outcomes focus on the influence of masonry patterns and demonstrate how irregularity of units can
22 affect the structural response leading to a reduction in terms of strength and ductility if compared to
23 regular distribution of masonry units.

24 **Keywords:** Unreinforced masonry structures; Mesoscale approach; non-periodic masonry pattern;
25 DMEM.
26

27 **1 Introduction**

28 Field reconnaissance after earthquake events demonstrated how out-of-plane (OOP) failure mechanisms
29 affect historical unreinforced masonry (URM) structures, producing their collapse, loss of life, and, at
30 the same time, an immaterial loss of memory and people identity [1]–[3]. As a consequence, in the last
31 decades, several researchers proposed advanced analysis methods, often calibrated through extensive
32 experimental campaigns [4]–[9], for the preventive assessment of heritage buildings. Their overall
33 classification is mainly made between numerical and analytical approaches [10], [11].

34 Analytical approaches are often based on limit analysis theorems that have the great advantage of being
35 independent of most material properties but inevitably rely on a very simplified material model [12]–
36 [15]. Such approaches include force- and displacement-based procedures suitable for rapid seismic
37 vulnerability assessment. Moreover, limit analysis-based tools typically neglect the structure's global
38 behaviour, only focusing on assessing a set of local failure mechanisms [16]–[20].

39 Numerical approaches are typically implemented in the Finite Element Method (FEM) [21]–[27] or
40 Discrete Element Method (DEM) [28]–[32] frameworks. Such approaches model the masonry material
41 using different representation scales, i.e., equivalent continuum, macro-blocks, or discrete
42 representations. FEM allows a more versatile application as masonry can be represented either through
43 a homogeneous equivalent media (designated macro-modelling) or by a discrete representation of units
44 and joints (designated micro-modelling). DEM is well suited for masonries with both dry- and mortared
45 joints but still requires a full representation of the blocks (masonry units) arrangement [32]–[37]. In
46 both cases, linear and nonlinear static and dynamic analyses are eligible.

47 Nonetheless, additionally, to the significant amount of data needed to characterise the nonlinear
48 response of materials, the analysis can be both time-consuming and computationally expensive when
49 estimating the ultimate ductility level of the structure. Despite their reliability, the computational
50 efficiency of the available numerical methods is rarely compatible with the need to have a rigorous real-
51 time post-earthquake assessment [38]. Hence, several research groups developed alternative modelling
52 approaches and practical tools to decrease the computational cost of nonlinear static and dynamic
53 analyses [39]–[42].

54 In this framework, macro-element approaches were proposed in which structures are described as an
55 assemblage of macroscopic structural elements. For instance, the Equivalent Frame Model (EFM) is
56 being adopted by national and international standards in combination with nonlinear static analysis [43].
57 Because of its simplicity and low computational demand, it is one of the most widely adopted analysis
58 methods in engineering practice [44]. However, despite the advantages of the EFM method, it is worth
59 underlining some limitations: i) discretisation of structure with an irregular position of openings is
60 sometimes ambiguous or not possible, ii) geometric inconsistency of the approach, as it represents a
61 plane portion such as masonry panels with a mono-dimensional element, iii) presence of areas which
62 cannot be damaged, generally identified as rigid links, iv) the ultimate displacement is a priori defined.

63 In order to cover such limitations and keep the computational efficiency, a discrete macro-element
64 method (DMEM) was proposed in Ref. [45]. The first implementation of the DMEM approach was
65 based on a plane element whose kinematics was described only by four Lagrangian parameters: three
66 degrees of freedom associated with the in-plane (IP) rigid-body motion and one additional degree of
67 freedom related to shear deformability in its own plane. Such plane elements were represented by
68 articulated quadrilaterals with rigid edges connected to the vertices by four hinges and diagonal springs
69 simulating the shear behaviour. Each element was connected to the adjacent ones by means of a discrete
70 distribution of nonlinear springs, denoted as interfaces. The interfaces' deformations are associated with
71 the relative motion of the connected panels, and no additional Lagrangian parameters are needed. One
72 can note how this preliminary formulation of the DMEM approach simulated the nonlinear behaviour
73 of masonry panels IP, not being able to describe the out-of-plane (OOP) behaviour. The reliability of
74 the proposed approach was evaluated by means of nonlinear incremental static analysis performed on
75 masonry structures, for which theoretical and/or experimental results are available in the literature [45].
76 Afterwards, the macro-element was improved to investigate OOP response of URM structure by
77 developing a three-dimensional macro-element for which its kinematic was described by seven degrees
78 of freedom IP and OOP [46]. Subsequently, such an element was adopted to simulate also curved
79 masonry structures, whose role is fundamental both in the local and global behaviour of the buildings,
80 especially in the monumental ones (e.g. arches, vaults, and domes) [47]. Both experimental and
81 numerical validations showed the capability of the proposed approach to be applied to predict the

82 nonlinear response of URM structures under different loading conditions. A more recent
83 implementation was conducted to assess the seismic behaviour of URM structures subjected to dynamic
84 input, i.e., earthquakes records, by introducing a consistent or lumped mass matrix [48]. As
85 demonstrated in Ref. [48], the DMEM strategy showed its capability to simulate dynamic response
86 characterised by coupling IP/OOP failure mechanisms. Despite the improvements recently
87 implemented in the DMEM approach, some limitations still characterised such a methodology, i.e., i)
88 formulation accounts only for small displacements, ii) macro elements size dependency when the
89 structure is affected by OOP loading, iii) vertical joints do not permit to account for interlocking
90 phenomenon typically expected in masonry structures. However, the literature analysis underlines how
91 the DMEM approach may be used to assess the seismic behaviour of historic masonry structures.
92 Nevertheless, just a few attempts investigated the influence of the mesh discretisation of the macro-
93 elements, how the same impacts the structural response, and the potential in adopting a mesoscale
94 representation [49]. In order to address these gaps, this paper mainly aims to: i) apply the DMEM
95 approach by adopting a mesh representation consistent with real masonry patterns and ii) evaluate what
96 phenomenon affects the structural response. To accomplish the latter, the framework described next has
97 been followed:

- 98 1. The 3D macro-element is adopted to simulate the OOP response of masonry structures.
- 99 2. Parametric investigations are performed on U-shape masonry prototypes made with stone [50].
100 Modelling parameters are investigated and discussed, and the motivation in using mesoscale
101 mesh discretisation is underlined.
- 102 3. A random mesh generator is implemented to quickly generate numerical models where the
103 masonry patterns are consistent with a chaotic distribution of the units.
- 104 4. The random mesh generator tool is used to generate ten different masonry patterns consistent
105 with a unique parent geometry. The masonry prototypes differ only in terms of masonry patterns
106 and openings.

107 The novelties of the study include: i) a pioneering application of the mesoscale random generated
108 masonry pattern representation in DMEM for simulating unreinforced masonry structures, ii) numerical

109 investigation of the phenomenon that affects the structural response when mesoscale representation is
110 adopted, and iii) implementation of a visual script for the generation of different masonry wall patterns.
111 The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 summarises the theoretical formulation and the numerical
112 implementation of the DMEM approach. Section 3 presents a parametric study to assess how the mesh
113 topology affects the structural response and reports comparisons between classical DMEM and finite
114 element homogenous approaches. Section 4 investigates how different degrees of randomness affects
115 the seismic behaviour of a benchmark case. Finally, conclusions are discussed in Section 5.

116 **2 Discrete Macro-Element Modelling Approach**

117 As mentioned in the previous section, the original formulation of the DMEM approach provided only
118 the possibility to simulate the IP structural response of masonry panels, which were modelled using a
119 simple plane element (Figure 1a). In order to overcome this issue, a macro-element that was able to
120 simulate the OOP response was proposed in Ref. [47]. Such a macro-element is a zero-thickness
121 element, which is able to account for shear deformation in its plane, having on the edges a set of different
122 nonlinear links denoted as interfaces. Each interface is constituted by i) m rows of n orthogonal
123 nonlinear links, responsible for simulating the panels' flexural behaviour (Figure 1b and Figure 1c), ii)
124 a single IP sliding link, which rules for the sliding behaviour, and iii) a set of two OOP sliding links
125 that account for both OOP sliding and torsional behaviour. One can note that the number of orthogonal
126 links is selected in accordance with the desired level of accuracy, losing as a counterpart a little
127 computational efficiency. The diagonal shear deformability is governed by a diagonal nonlinear link
128 that connects two corners of the quad element [46]. Hence, the kinematics of the spatial macro-element
129 are described by seven Lagrangian parameters, six governing the rigid body motion and the remaining
130 associated with the IP shear deformability. One can note that the low number of DOFs associated with
131 each macro-element makes this approach computationally inexpensive with respect to the classical
132 FEM and DEM formulations.

133 Figure 1: DMEM evolution (a) Plane Element; (b) Regular Spatial Element; (c) Irregular Spatial Element.

134 Macro-element's nonlinear links calibration has been performed according to a straightforward fibre
 135 calibration procedure. The procedure reported herein is suitable for three-dimensional model
 136 characterised by elements with the same geometrical and mechanical characteristics. Nevertheless, the
 137 calibration procedure of nonlinear links associated with irregular three-dimensional panels
 138 characterized by different mechanical properties presents a more sophisticated procedure beyond this
 139 research's scope. A detailed description of the calibration procedure for irregular macro-elements, can
 140 be found in Ref. [51]. The nonlinear interface's links can be distinguished as transversal N-links, IP
 141 shear sliding N-link, and OOP shear sliding N-links. In the following, the main characteristics of the
 142 calibration procedure are described with reference to each group of nonlinear N-links.

143 Transversal N-links orthogonal to the interfaces govern the flexural IP and OOP behaviour between
 144 two adjacent macro-elements. Each orthogonal link is representative of the nonlinear behaviour of the
 145 corresponding masonry strip of two adjacent elements (e.g. panels l and k) along a given material
 146 direction. Since the deformations of the panels are concentrated in the zero-thickness interfaces, the
 147 orthogonal links have the role of simulating the deformability of the two connected panels in a given
 148 direction. It is worth noting that to account for masonry as an orthotropic material, the calibration is
 149 conducted separately for horizontal and vertical interface elements. The initial stiffness K_n of each link
 150 is simply obtained by assigning, to each link, the axial rigidity (Young's modulus, E) of the
 151 corresponding masonry strip defined by the volume characterised by the influence area (A_{Sn}) of each
 152 spring and half of the length ($L/2$) of the panel (Figure 2a). This procedure provides a couple of springs

153 in series, each associated with each of the connected panels. Each couple of springs is then replaced by
154 a single resulting nonlinear spring as described in [45]. The yielding forces in tension, F_{ym} , and
155 compression, F_{ycn} , of each transversal link are related to their influence area and the tensile, σ_t , and
156 compressive strengths, σ_c , adopted for the masonry. Finally, the tensile and compressive yieldind
157 displacements u_{ym} and u_{ycn} are associated with each link's yielding forces and initial stiffness. The
158 nonlinear behaviour of the masonry can be simulated by adopting for transversal links any suitable and
159 uniaxial nonlinear constitutive laws. Initial stiffness, tensile and compressive strength and displacement
160 are reported respectively in Eq. 1-5.

$$161 \quad K_n = 2 \frac{EA_{Sn}}{L} \quad (1)$$

$$162 \quad F_{ytn} = A_{Sn}\sigma_t \quad (2)$$

$$163 \quad F_{ycn} = A_{Sn}\sigma_c \quad (3)$$

$$164 \quad u_{ytn} = \frac{F_{ytn}}{K_n} \quad (4)$$

$$165 \quad u_{ycn} = \frac{F_{ycn}}{K_n} \quad (5)$$

166 The shear deformation of a masonry wall, discretised by a mesh of macro-elements, can be partly related
167 to the diagonal shear deformation and partly due to the friction sliding along the interface between two
168 adjacent macro-elements. The former is governed by a single diagonal spring (Figure 1) connecting two
169 opposite macro-elements vertexes. First, a linear elastic calibration is performed by enforcing the
170 equivalence between the macro-element subjected to a pure shear deformation related to the kinematic
171 of the hinged quadrilateral and a reference continuous elastic solid. This finite portion of masonry is
172 characterised by shear modulus G , transversal area A_t , height h , and base b . The initial stiffness K_D of
173 the diagonal link is expressed in Equation 6, in which θ is defined as $\arctan(b/h)$, and it is influenced by
174 a shear factor denoted as α_s , whose value ranges between 0 and 1. If this factor presents a value equal to
175 1, the global in-plane shear stiffness is entirely associated with the initial stiffness of the diagonal links,
176 and the in-plane sliding links are assumed rigid. On the other hand, if the value of α is different from 1,
177 the global in-plane shear stiffness comes as a contribution between diagonal and in-plane sliding
178 nonlinear links.

179
$$K_D = \frac{G \cdot A_t}{h \cdot \cos^2 \theta \cdot \alpha_s} \quad (6)$$

180 The nonlinear post-elastic behaviour may be addressed by adopting different and suitable constitutive
 181 laws. A Mohr-Coulomb or Turnsek-Cacovic yielding criteria can be adopted for the constitutive
 182 calibration of this nonlinear link. The value of yielding force F_y associated to the Mohr-Coulomb and
 183 Turnsek and Cacovic [52] criteria are given by Equations 7 and 8, respectively.

184
$$F_y = F_{y0} + \mu_d \cdot N \quad (7)$$

185
$$F_y = F_{v0} \sqrt{1 + \frac{N}{1.5 \cdot F_{v0}}} \quad (8)$$

186 where F_{y0} and F_{v0} are the yielding forces under no confinement conditions (zero normal stresses)
 187 associated with the Mohr-Coulomb or Turnsek-Cacovic criteria.

188 The IP and OOP shear sliding springs (Figure 2b) rule the relative sliding motion between two adjacent
 189 macro-elements. The initial stiffness K_S , related to the sliding mechanism, is associated with the panel's
 190 shear modulus G , the effective length, and the influence area A_s of the corresponding nonlinear link.
 191 The expression that provides the initial stiffness for IP and OOP sliding links is given by Equation 9. It
 192 is worth mentioning that the OOP shear mechanism is solely associated with the nonlinear links along
 193 the thickness of the interface element, and there is no need to introduce a shear factor in the out-of-
 194 plane direction. The OOP sliding links also account for torsional behaviour around the axis orthogonal
 195 to the interface plane (Figure 2c). The elastic torsional stiffness K_ϕ is associated with a torsional rigidity
 196 factor J_ϕ given by Equation 11, in which s corresponds to the thickness of the panel. The shear sliding
 197 behaviour of UMR structure is associated with a frictional phenomenon along the mortar joints. Such
 198 behaviour can be adequately simulated by means of a Mohr-Coulomb yielding criterion. Based on this
 199 approach, the current yielding force F_y of the IP and OOP links is defined employing the cohesion c
 200 and friction coefficient μ_s of the masonry material, the current contact area A , and the normal force N
 201 applied to the interface element.

202
$$K_S = \frac{G \cdot A_s}{L \cdot (1 - \alpha_s)} \quad (9)$$

203

204

205

206

$$K_{\phi} = \frac{G \cdot J_{\phi}}{L} \quad (10)$$

207

$$J_{\phi} = B \cdot s^3 \left[\frac{1}{3} - 0.21 \frac{s}{B} \left(1 - \frac{s^4}{12 \cdot B^4} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

208

$$F_y = c \cdot A + \mu_s \cdot N \quad (12)$$

209

210

211

212

213

214

More details on the calibration procedures can be found in Refs. [45], [46]. One can note that different nonlinear constitutive laws for the shear mechanisms accounting for residual strength when a target displacement is attained might be adopted. However, it has not been considered in the present paper since the main goal of this study relies on the investigation of the masonry mesoscale masonry pattern representation in a DMEM approach. For this reason, simple constitutive laws have been adopted aiming at limiting the number of parameters involved in the numerical analyses.

215

216

Figure 2: Interface's Links representation: (a) Orthogonal N-Links; (b) In-plane sliding N-links; (c) Out-of-Plane sliding N-Links.

217

218

DMEM approach classical interpretation implies that each macro-element must be representative of the corresponding finite portion of masonry walls, according to the macro-modelling approach.

219 Consequently, there is no relation between masonry constituents and block regions, and a
220 homogenisation strategy is adopted to define the masonry mechanical constitutive law.
221 An example of a masonry wall is shown in Figure 3a. Even though DMEM is conceived as a macro-
222 modelling strategy, some studies (Figure 3b) explored the possibility of discretising the structural model
223 within a mesoscale approach (Figure 3c) [49], [53]. In this case, the properties of the constituents, for
224 example, brick and mortar, and the details of the masonry arrangement are adopted to study the
225 interaction of the constituents and the damage propagation pattern under different loading histories. It
226 is worth noting that by using mesoscale strategies, some physical phenomena involved can be described
227 in more detail, i.e. interlocking effect between the blocks or the presence of well-defined and realistic
228 fracture surfaces at the interface. Moreover, a mesoscale model is quite accurate for the study of weak
229 or dry mortar masonry structures for which usually DEM approaches are adopted [28], [29], [54].
230 Therefore, depending on whether a macro- or mesoscale approach is adopted, it is necessary to
231 appropriately calibrate the main mechanical parameters that influence the response. As reported in Ref.
232 [49], the interlocking phenomenon has mainly the effects of increasing the tensile strength and the
233 cohesion between blocks influencing the collapse mechanism and increasing the strength and
234 displacement capacity of the entire structure.

(c)

235 Figure 3: (a) Real blocks' arrangement; (b) Macro-scale modelling; (c) Mesoscale modelling.

236

237 3 Numerical Investigation: U-shape Stone Prototype

238 3.1 Description of the prototype

239 In this section, parametric studies are performed to assess how the mesh topology affects numerical
 240 simulations performed with the DMEM. The numerical investigation has been performed on a
 241 benchmark represented by a U-shape masonry prototype, a simple structure of three walls forming a U-
 242 plan made in stone masonry that idealises the experimental tests performed at the LNEC shaking table
 243 [55]. Figure 4 represents the overall geometrical characteristic of the masonry prototype.

244 Figure 4: U-Shape stone prototype: geometrical features.
 245

246 Figure 5 represents the different mesh discretisations adopted. Three of them are mesh discretisations
 247 consistent with the macroscale approach, in which the macro-elements' characteristic dimension is
 248 gradually decreased to reach three different levels of refinement. The last one is a mesoscale
 249 discretisation, which is taken in agreement with the one adopted in Ref. [56]. Concerning the
 250 mechanical properties, the parameters reported in Ref. [56] have been initially adopted for all mesh
 251 discretisations (Table 1 and
 252 Table 2). It is worth underlining that when a mesoscale representation is adopted (M4), a linear-elastic
 253 constitutive law has been selected for the diagonal shear behaviour to avoid that diagonal cracking
 254 involves the single macro element. This assumption ensures that the shear failure does not occur when
 255 macro-element represents a single masonry unit [49].

256 Figure 5: Mesh discretisations adopted for the numerical investigations.

257
 258 Table 1: Mechanical properties adopted for the U-shape prototype: flexural behaviour [56].

Model	Flexural behaviour					
	Density [kg/m ³]	Young's modulus [MPa]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Compressive fracture energy [N/mm]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Tensile fracture energy [N/mm]
M1,M2,M3	2360	2077	5.44	∞	0.224	0.048
M4	2360	2077	5.44	∞	0.224	0.048

259
 260 Table 2: Mechanical properties adopted for the U-shape prototype: shear behaviour [56].

Model	Diagonal cracking behaviour			Sliding behaviour		
	Shear modulus [MPa]	Failure criterion	τ_0 [MPa]	μ_d	c [MPa]	μ_s
M1,M2,M3	830	Mohr-Coulomb	0.336	0.3	0.336	0.3
M4	830	-	-	-	0.336	0.3

261

262 **3.2 Nonlinear static analyses**

263 This section aims to investigate how the structural response of macro- and mesoscale masonry
264 representations are adopted. Nonlinear static analyses have been performed applying vertical actions
265 including gravity loads and, subsequently, an incremental lateral force along the positive direction of
266 axis X.

267 Figure 6a reports the load-displacement curves of the considered mesh discretisations for horizontal
268 actions. Further comparison is provided with a homogeneous model performed in Abaqus [57] where
269 concrete damage plasticity (CDP) has been adopted to simulate the nonlinear behaviour of the masonry.

270 The results demonstrate how the M1, M2 and M3 models are slightly affected by a mesh dependency,
271 showing small differences in terms of initial stiffness and peak load. On the contrary, the mesoscale
272 model, i.e., M4, provides a stiffer initial behaviour and a higher peak load than the M1, M2 and M3.
273 One can note how M4 has the same initial stiffness as the homogeneous model performed in Abaqus;
274 however, the reached peak load is slightly higher than the macroscale discretisations, which cannot
275 account for blocks' interlocking. When mesh discretisation with interlocking between blocks are
276 considered, the structural response is characterised by a complex interaction between the macro-
277 elements that involved shear sliding, shear diagonal, torsional, and membrane behaviour.

278 The mesoscale model M4 correctly accounts for the stone's interlocking effects leading to higher
279 stiffness and ultimate load. Moreover, M1, M2 and M3 present similar post-peak behaviour, while M4
280 has two drops. Generally, when a discrete numerical model is used, each drop corresponds to a local
281 crack in the numerical model. Once again, the differences in the post-peak behaviour can be justified
282 by the fact that the mesoscale model M4 correctly accounts for the stone's interlocking effects, leading
283 to different and more realistic results in terms of loading-displacement curve and collapse mechanism.
284 In this latter model, the first drop, in the loading-displacement curve, is due to the crack propagation
285 that starts from the opening in the later wall, whereas the second drop is related to the flexural rocking
286 mechanism of the orthogonal wall without openings in its plane, which causes compressive and tensile
287 stresses at the base of the wall. When the tensile stress exceeds the tensile strength assumed for the

288 masonry, cracks propagate at the base of the wall. M4 model grasps the so-called flange effect that can
 289 cause a significant overstrength on the approach based on equivalent frame modelling [58].
 290 The misalignment of the vertical interfaces of the model M4 leads to more realistic results also in terms
 291 of collapse mechanisms, as reported in Figure 7, where the failure mechanisms provided by the five
 292 considered models are compared. To this end, for taking into account the interlocking effects provided
 293 by the mesoscales model by using a macroscale simulation, it is needed to consider the over-stiffness
 294 and over-strength in the calibration of the mechanical parameters, particularly when the size of the units
 295 is large in comparison of the size of the structural components of the building. According to Ref. [31],
 296 the tensile strength and fracture energy have been modified to obtain pushover curves comparable to
 297 those relative to the mesoscale model. Hence, the updated macroscale model (DMEM-C) has the same
 298 mesh discretisation adopted for M1, whereas tensile strength and fracture energy were calibrated
 299 through a tuned process, which was stopped when assumed a value equal to 0.240 MPa and 0.060
 300 N/mm, respectively.

301
 302 Figure 6: (a) Comparison in terms of load-displacement curve; (b) Normalised computational time (CPU) and
 303 normalised number of degrees-of-freedom (DOFs) for each numerical simulation.

304 One can note how M4 and DMEM-C curves show a different initial stiffness. Such a phenomenon may
 305 be mitigated by also modifying the elastic modulus of the masonry in the DMEM-C model. Finally,
 306 Figure 6b reports a comparison including the required computational time (CPU) and the number of
 307 degrees-of-freedom (DOFs) for each mesh discretisation. Results have been normalised with respect to
 308 the Abaqus model. It should be noted how the DMEM approach can strongly decrease the

309 computational demand, by more than 90%. Besides, when a mesoscale mesh representation has been
310 used, the computational saving is more than 95%, while the amount of DOFs is decreased by 90%.

311 Figure 7: Comparison in terms of failure mechanisms.

312 In short, the mesoscale representation may be a powerful alternative to model unreinforced masonry
313 structures within a discrete macro-element approach (particularly if compared with classic
314 homogeneous FE methodologies), even though the mechanical calibration cannot be performed
315 considering an equivalent homogenous masonry, as described in the previous section 2. Differently, a
316 proper characterisation of the blocks and the mortar joints must be considered.

317 **4 Numerical Investigation: Box prototype**

318 **4.1 Generation of the models: geometrical and mechanical characteristics**

319 As reported in Ref. [59], masonry constituted by the assemblage of blocks and stones with variable
320 dimensions is very common in historical buildings. However, the complexity of the problem, and the
321 amount of information to accurately model using a mesoscale approach, usually preclude the study of
322 these structures deterministically. Indeed, such uncertainties suggest investigations based on
323 probabilistic approaches rather than deterministic, i.e., assuming texture properties within certain
324 statistical variations.

325 This section is devoted to understanding how irregular masonry patterns affect the structural response
326 of a masonry prototype having a rectangular shape. Several mesh discretisations having a different
327 degree of randomness have been generated by adopting a proper numerical tool which is described
328 below. Instead, the parent geometry is always the same and coherent with a rectangular plan having
329 4.80 m and 7.20 m, with walls' height equal to 4.0 m and a walls' thickness of 0.30 m (Figure 8). The

330 overload arising from a deformable slab, having a weight equal to 150 kN/m², has been modelled as
331 distributed line load along the top of the walls W2 (Figure 8).

332
333 Figure 8: Parent geometry for box prototype: geometrical features.

334 The masonry patterns have been generated using a numerical tool implemented in a GHPython script
335 [42], [43]. It can generate 2D or 3D masonry prototypes within a randomised masonry pattern. However,
336 one can note that the GHPython script is responsible for generating a single planar wall, whereas the
337 assemblages in 3D still require operations performed that have been manually implemented. Next, the
338 tool's explanation is performed in 2D framework, i.e., referred to the generation of a single planar wall.
339 As represented in Figure 9a, the primary tool's inputs are the overall dimension of the wall (height,
340 length and width), the cantonal's dimension, and the number of units' courses (N_R). At this stage, the
341 user has to define some parameters defining three numerical domains. As reported in Figure 9b the first
342 domain is formed by integer numbers that define the minimum and the maximum number of units per
343 row (U_R). The second domain of values is defined by the smallest and the largest unit length that may
344 appear at each row (U_L). Finally, the third domain, similar to the second one, is defined by the minimum
345 and maximum height that may assume a units' course (U_H) (Figure 9c). Finally, the total height of the
346 wall is scaled in order to be consistent with the primary input of the generator. The proposed algorithm
347 can randomise the values contained inside the early mentioned domains and generate a different
348 masonry pattern at each iteration.

349

350 Figure 9: Random masonry pattern generation.

351 Referring to the parent geometry reported in Figure 8, one can note that two subcategories of masonry
 352 patterns have been generated, which are characterised by a different number on the units' courses equal
 353 to (A) 18 and (B) 12, respectively. The investigated mesh configurations are reported in Figure 10. A
 354 regular masonry bond pattern characterises the reference configurations A1 and B1, where all the units
 355 have the same dimensions, i.e., $0.60 \times 0.222 \times 0.30 \text{ m}^3$ and $0.60 \times 0.333 \times 0.30 \text{ m}^3$, respectively.

356 A chaotic mesh distribution instead characterises A2 and B2 configurations. Therefore, the following
 357 values for the domains U_R and U_L have been adopted:

358
$$U_R^{W1} = [6, 10] \quad (13)$$

359
$$U_R^{W2} = [9, 15] \quad (14)$$

360
$$U_L^{W1,W2} = [[0.20, 0.60], 1.00] \quad (15)$$

361 where the limits $W1$ and $W2$ are referred to walls having smaller and larger lengths (see Figure 9). One
 362 can note how $U_L^{W1,W2}$ does not contain the actual dimension of the blocks, but the ratio between a lower
 363 bound, which has been assumed to be randomly selected between 0.20 and 0.60, and the upper bound
 364 that is equal to 1.00. The value selection is random and is performed by using the random function
 365 available in Python [60]. Hence, a remapping procedure must be performed in order to respect the
 366 compatibility condition regarding geometry:

367
$$\sum_{U_R} U_L / (L - L_{cant}) = 1 \quad (16)$$

368 Finally, A3 and B3 are also affected by a variable height of the units' courses. In this case, the domain
 369 U_H has been defined as follow:

370
$$U_H = [0.50, 1.00] \quad (17)$$

371 One can note that U_H does not contain the actual height of the unit's course, but the ratio between a
 372 lower bound, assumed to be 0.50, and the upper bound that is equal to 1.00. Hence, a remapping
 373 procedure must be again performed in order to respect the following compatibility condition:

374
$$\sum_{N_R} U_H/(H) = 1 \tag{18}$$

375 Finally, the openings are added by making Boolean differences and introducing the lintels.

376
377 Figure 10: Mesh discretisations adopted for the numerical investigations, with a total of ten.

378 As mentioned in section 2, DMEM approach requires defining the mechanical properties considering
379 the failure modes, i.e., flexural, shear-diagonal and shear-sliding, independently. A
380 nonlinear constitutive law has been assumed for the flexural response, governed by an exponential
381 softening for the tensile post-peak behaviour and a parabolic curve for the compressive post-peak
382 behaviour. The shear-sliding behaviour has been considered according to a Mohr-Coulomb failure
383 criterion, considering a perfectly post-elastic constitutive law and assuming that the cohesion under no
384 confinement conditions is equal to the tensile strength. Regarding the shear-diagonal behaviour, a
385 linear-elastic constitutive law has been adopted to avoid the shear failure of the element, i.e., a
386 mesoscale approach [56] without accounting for the failure of the units (assumed infinitely resistant).
387 Table 3 and Table 4 summarise the mechanical properties adopted across the numerical simulation. One
388 can note how tensile strength and fracture energy have been assumed to be very small to simulate dry-
389 stacked masonry.

390 Table 3: Mechanical properties adopted for the box prototype: flexural behaviour

	Flexural behaviour					
	Density	Young's modulus	Compressive strength	Compressive fracture energy	Tensile strength	Tensile fracture energy
Model	[kg/m ³]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[N/mm]	[MPa]	[N/mm]
Mesoscale	1800	1500	3.80	3.00	0.001	0.0001

391
392
393 Table 4: Mechanical properties adopted for the box prototype: shear behaviour

	Diagonal cracking behaviour			Sliding behaviour		
	Shear modulus	Failure criterion	τ_0	μ_d	c	μ_s
Model	[MPa]		[MPa]		[MPa]	
Mesoscale	580	-	-	-	0.001	0.6

394

395 4.2 Nonlinear static analysis

396 Nonlinear static analyses have been performed applying an incremental lateral force, proportional to
397 the mass of the structure, in X+ direction (Figure 8). Figure 8 also represents the control point used to
398 define the pushover curves, which corresponds to the middle node at the top of the longitudinal wall
399 that exhibits the maximum out of plane displacement.

400 Figure 11a and Figure 11b report the pushover curves for classes A and B characterised by a different
401 number on the units' courses equal to 18 and 12, respectively. As stated above, for each class, five
402 masonry patterns characterised by an increased index of randomness and the presence of openings have
403 been generated (Figure 10). Results demonstrate how irregular masonry patterns, as well as the presence
404 of the openings, tend to decrease the capacity of the structures.

405 As mentioned earlier, reference macro-element mesh discretisation has been compared with the random
406 generated models (A2, A3, B2, B3) as well as with regular mesoscale configuration (A1, B1). To this
407 end, reverse engineering was considered for selected mechanical parameters to get a good match in
408 terms of structural response between macroscale and mesoscale models. In order to simulate the
409 interlocking effect, in the macroscale model, the shear-diagonal behaviour has been calibrated
410 according to a Turnsek-Cacovic failure criterion assuming a perfectly post-elastic law. The shear
411 strength in the absence of axial load has been assumed to be equal 0.2 MPa while a value of 0.6 has
412 been considered for the friction coefficient μ_s . The tensile strength f_t and the cohesion c , which affected
413 the peak of the capacity curve, have been increased to 0.025 MPa in macro-model A and to 0.015 MPa
414 in macro-model B with the aim to satisfactorily reproduce the static nonlinear response of the mesoscale
415 models A1 and B1, respectively. Moreover, the value of tensile fracture energy G_{ft} , which influenced
416 the post-peak capacity as reported in Ref. [49], was increased to 0.25 and 0.30 N/mm in the constitutive
417 law of model A and B, respectively. It is worth noting that the interlocking phenomenon effect on the
418 initial stiffness is less pronounced than the previously analysed U-shape. It happens because the
419 interlocking phenomenon tends to increase the structure's initial stiffness, particularly when the
420 slenderness ratio is small.

421

422 Figure 11: Comparison in terms of load-displacement curves for classes A and B characterised by a different
 423 number on the units' courses equal to: (a) 18; (b) 12.

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Furthermore, the deformed shapes at the last step of the analyses, highlighting the collapse mechanisms of the structures and the concentration of plastic strains, are reported in Figure 12. The failure mechanisms are always characterised by the overturning of the wall orthogonally loaded and subjected to outwards actions. In this regard, it is observed how the plastic strains are mainly concentrated at the connection with the sidewalls. It is worth noting how increasing the randomness index, the collapse mechanism is more localised at a single wall, and the structure tends to rapidly lose the box behaviour, whereas, in the structure with a regular masonry pattern, the overall structural behaviour is affected by a more global character although the incipient collapse mechanism is still characterised by the collapse of the wall that tends to overturn OOP.

A1

B1

433
 434 Figure 12: Deformed shapes of the mesh discretisations adopted for control point displacement equal to 100 mm.

435 For the sake of clarity, the histogram reported in Figure 13 represents the maximum displacement
 436 reached at the end of the simulations for the mesh configuration A1_o and A3_o evaluated by monitoring
 437 two control points located in the middle of the two opposite long walls. The same analysis has been

438 reported regarding the configuration B1_o and B3_o. In both cases, the results have been normalised with
 439 respect to the greater of the maximum displacements reached by the two points, and they quantitatively
 440 demonstrate how a chaotic distribution tends to localise the collapse mechanism leading to a negative
 441 influence on the masonry prototypes' global behaviour.

442
 443 Figure 13: Comparisons in terms of maximum displacement reached: orange vs blue control point. Notation 1
 444 indicates a regular masonry pattern and notation 3 indicates an irregular masonry pattern.

445 4.3 Nonlinear dynamic analysis

446 In this section, dynamic simulations have been performed applying a semi-sinusoidal pulse with an
 447 amplitude equal to 1g and a frequency of 6.7 Hz (that is a frequency close to the first mode vibration of
 448 the model A1) as input ground motion along the X direction (see Figure 14). Newmark's method with
 449 parameters $\gamma = 0.5$ and $\beta = 0.25$ [61], and a time step of 0.005 s has been adopted as numerical
 450 integration procedure, whereas the energy dissipation was based on the Rayleigh viscous damping
 451 criterion [62], assuming a 5% damping ratio associated with the 1st and 13th natural frequencies, the
 452 latter corresponding to 80% of the total accumulated specimen mass.

453

454 Figure 14: Ground motion input: semi-sinusoidal pulse.

455 Figure 15 a and b report the time-history displacement of the control point of the mesoscale patterns

456 belonging to classes A and B. Similar to what is underlined within the nonlinear static analyses (with

457 lower capacity in terms of forces), the mesh discretisations belonging to class B (low number of units'

458 courses) show higher residual displacements. Indeed, B models are affected statistically by a smaller m

459 parameter, i.e., the ratio between the half-length and height of the blocks, being class B characterised

460 by fewer courses. It results in an overall lower capability of the blocks to generate frictional resistance

461 in their plane [63].

(a)

(b)

462

463 Figure 15: Comparison in terms of time history displacement.

464 Figure 15a and Figure 15b show how increasing the masonry pattern's randomness, the structures are
 465 affected by larger displacements. Similarly, larger displacements are found in cases with openings, for
 466 which the structures are obviously affected by lower global stiffness. Finally, aiming to investigate the
 467 dynamic response of the considered specimens when subjected to earthquake loading, incremental
 468 dynamic analysis (IDA) has been carried out by adopting the Amatrice EW (2016) earthquake record,
 469 Italy, as input ground motion active along the X-direction (see Figure 16a). The original record has been
 470 scaled in order to reach the condition of the near-collapse of the investigated masonry prototype.

471
 472 Figure 16: (a) Amatrice EW (2016) record; (b) ratio between the maximum displacement of the control point and
 473 the absolute maximum displacement for all mesh discretisations as a function of the scale factor of the record:
 474 shaded red provides the envelope of the results.

475 Figure 16b reports the ratio between the maximum displacement of the control point and the absolute
 476 maximum displacement for all the investigated adopted mesh discretisations as a function of the scale
 477 factor of the record, which is a measure of the ground motion intensity (IM). It should be underlined
 478 that the adopted mesh configurations have shown a divergent behaviour with the increase of the scale
 479 factor, pointing out that the influence of the mesh pattern is larger, in terms of the maximum reached
 480 displacement, for a higher value of PGA. The results also confirm the need to perform stochastic
 481 simulations by generating a large number of masonry pattern configurations statistically consistent.

482 **5 Final remarks**

483 This paper investigates the DMEM approach by adopting a mesoscale representation rather than a
484 classical macroscale representation. At first, parametric analyses investigate the mesh sensitivity of the
485 DMEM approach and shed light on the mechanical parameters that need to be calibrated to consider
486 physical phenomena, namely interlocking behaviour generated by the vertical joint misalignment. Such
487 investigations were performed by using a benchmark model represented by a U-shape masonry
488 prototype made in stone, idealising the experimental tests performed at the LNEC shaking table [55].
489 The results underlined the need to recalibrate the tensile fracture energy as well as the tensile strength.
490 Furthermore, the comparisons with a classical FE homogeneous model calibrated in ABAQUS showed
491 that DMEM requires much lower computational demand, also if the adopted discrete modelling
492 approach contemplated a unit by unit mesoscale modelling.

493 In order to adequately simulate URM structures characterised by units with variable dimensions, a
494 random masonry pattern generator was developed and implemented in a GHPython script. Such a script
495 was adopted to generate 10 masonry prototypes (with different level of randomness), with the overall
496 dimension consistent with a rectangular plan having 4.80 m and 7.20 m and walls' height equal to 4.0
497 m, in order to evaluate how the chaotic distribution of the units might affect the structural behaviour.
498 Both nonlinear static and dynamic analyses were performed, and the results demonstrated how the
499 masonry pattern affected the structural response. In particular, it was worth noting how the increase of
500 the randomness degree generated an early loss of the box behaviour.

501 The main conclusions of this study are that:

- 502 1. DMEM approach is able to take into account the main in-plane and out-of-plane failure
503 mechanisms;
- 504 2. Mesoscale configurations have been compared with a classical macro-element mesh
505 discretisation. To this end, it was necessary to calibrate some mechanical parameters in order
506 to get a good match in terms of structural response.
- 507 3. A digital tool was adopted to generate random masonry patterns; it can generate chaotic
508 masonry patterns by defining a few parameters.

- 509 4. The results demonstrated how the arrangement of the blocks affected the results. Moreover, by
510 increasing the randomness index, the collapse mechanism is localised, and the structures lose
511 the box behaviour, whereas, in the structure with a regular masonry pattern, the overall
512 structural behaviour exhibited a more global character.
- 513 5. Further investigations are necessary to better understand the potential of the DMEM approach
514 in handling a mesoscale model and to have a clear picture of the influence of mesh discretisation
515 on mechanical properties.
- 516 6. Further efforts are also required to implement a masonry pattern generator by taking into
517 account geometrical parameters easily detectable from practitioners, i.e., masonry quality index
518 [64].

519 Future studies could include: i) statistical definition of the mechanical properties [65], [66]; ii)
520 simulation of strengthening techniques, such as the use of Textile Reinforced Matrix (TRM) or Fiber
521 Reinforced Polymers (FRP) reinforcement, for masonry pattern having units of variable dimensions.

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526 Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Random mesh generator Visualisation, Supervision,
527 Validation, Writing—Original draft preparation, Writing—Reviewing and Editing. **Ivo Calìo:**
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